

European Researchers' Night 2024/2025

Communication Report D1.2. Awareness Campaign 2024

Project information

Project name	EU-EMBRACES
Full project name	Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools
Grant number	101162414
Project coordinator	ITQB NOVA
Project duration	20 months

Document information

Deliverable name and number	D1.2. Awareness Campaign 2024		
Due date	M7		
Actual submission date			
Authors	Mariana Campos (i3S), Júlio Borlido Santos (i3S), Rute Verdade (i3S)		
Contributing partners	IQTB NOVA, Ciência Viva		
Deliverable type	R	Document, report	X
	DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
	DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
	DMP	Data Management Plan	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Version history

Version	Date	Comments
1.0		

Index

1. Executive summary	4
2. Process and objectives	6
2.1 Strategic planning	6
2.2 Communication strategy implementation	6
3. Communication channels and strategies	8
3.1 Brand image	8
3.2 Overview of channels used	9
4. Metrics and evaluation	22
4.1 Digital platforms analytics	22
4.1.1 Website	22
4.1.1.1 Reformulation plan	23
4.1.2 Social media	25
4.2 Media coverage	29
4.3 Regional campaigns	31
4.4 Attendance and reach	34
5. Conclusion	37

1. | Executive summary

The European Researchers' Night (ERN) is an initiative promoted and funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Programme and European Research Executive Agency. The 2024 ERN project, called EU-EMBRACES – Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools, arises from the consortium coordinated by *Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier* – ITQB NOVA, together with the Institute for Research and Innovation in Health – i3S, and the Ciência Viva Network. This consortium, based in Portugal, aims to bridge the gap between researchers and the public, fostering curiosity, understanding, and appreciation for scientific research and the EU-Missions.

With the support from the European Union, the event was hosted in 9 cities across Portugal, drawing participants from diverse backgrounds, including students, families and educators. The event showcased hands-on activities, interactive science exhibitions, and engaging lectures, all designed to demystify scientific concepts and celebrate the vital role of research in society.

The ERN 2024 awareness campaign was designed to maximise visibility and engagement, targeting a broad audience through diverse media channels, social media platforms and direct partnerships. The strategy integrated multi-channel promotions and leveraged both digital and traditional media to build public interest and drive attention. Social media platforms each played a key role in connecting with specific audience segments, while the official ERN website provided centralised information and updates on all event activities. Additionally, collaborations with national and regional media, including newspapers and podcasts, extended our reach, establishing European Researchers' Night as a celebrated event across Portugal.

Key outcomes and highlights

- High reach: The ERN Project generated significant interest across media channels, with coverage in over **37** major channels, including television and online publications. Some of these were Público (digital newspaper with more than **47000** paid subscriptions) and CMTV (TV channel with more than **100000** viewers per day). A video promoting ERN was broadcast on RTP2 and RTP3 – Rádio e Televisão de Portugal channels. Together these channels represent 1,7% of the total audience shares in Portugal. Also, a digital advertisement in Público – Portuguese newspaper, reached more than **127000** impressions. Digital campaigns reached approximately **32000** users on social media, **8300** visitors on the website, and. Furthermore, more than **27000** people were made aware of ERN by participating in the **26** pre-events organised by all venues of this consortia. To add to the overall reach of the national communication efforts, each venue developed a local awareness campaign that complemented the first.
- Collaborative Efforts: The project brought together more than **650** researchers from nearly **100** academic institutions, research centres and associations across Portugal.

It fostered networking opportunities and strengthened partnerships with local organisations, enhancing the project's mission to promote science education and public engagement.

- High Engagement and Attendance: As a result of the awareness campaign, over **30000** participants attended the in-person and online activities hosted throughout the country. Families, in particular, showed a strong engagement with the event.

This consortium's approach to the biennium (2024-2025) reflects a commitment to making science accessible, inclusive, and engaging. By leveraging various communication channels and strategic partnerships, the project successfully achieved its primary objectives and contributed to the EU's goals of increasing public awareness and understanding of research and innovation. Looking ahead, the insights gained from this year's event will inform next year's edition of the European Researchers' Night, further improving the experience for participants and expanding the event's impact nationwide.

2. | Process and objectives

The ERN's event was designed to align with the European Union's goals for science outreach, with focus on accessibility, inclusivity, and interactivity. To ensure that ERN's objectives meet EU's goals, the ERN communication plan was designed to promote build-up activities and events, and coordinate the communication flow across all 9 venues. We followed a structured process composed of two main components: strategic planning and communication strategy implementation.

2.1 | Strategic planning

Initially, we outlined key objectives for the awareness campaign, aligning them with both the goals of the ERN project and the EU's vision for the ERN initiative. We aimed to:

- Increase the visibility of the event;
- Raise awareness for the day of the event, stimulating curiosity for the activities scheduled to take place;
- Encourage the participation of different audiences, of all ages and socioeconomic backgrounds, in pre-event activities and the event itself;
- Convey complex scientific concepts in attractive and simple formats so that a comfortable and inclusive environment is created for the community to learn;
- Show what the everyday life of a scientist could look like, deconstructing the idea typically associated with the profession;
- Highlight the practical importance of research and science in solving day-to-day problems;
- Spark audiences' curiosity, encouraging them to explore and question their surroundings;
- Foster an interest in science and in pursuing a scientific career.

Aligned with our objectives, we then identified core target audiences, including students, schools, preschool-aged children, families and the general adult population. Additionally, we targeted researchers, their associated institutions, traditional media outlets, and community and industry partners. Collaboration with these groups was essential as it enabled us to broaden our reach and expand the diversity of the activities offered.

2.2 | Communication strategy implementation

Based on our target audiences, we chose a multi-channel approach to maximise engagement. Channels included the ERN website, social media, newsletters, press releases, media partners and offline promotional materials. Each channel played a distinct role in reaching specific audience segments effectively.

The ERN website, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/>, was optimised to enhance user

experience and provide clear information about the project, pre-events and the main event. Despite these efforts, there were some issues detected on the website, which are currently being addressed. The intended improvements will result in a reformulation of the website for the remainder of the project.

Social media (**Instagram:** www.instagram.com/noitedosinvestigadores/; **Facebook:** www.facebook.com/neinvestigadores; **X:** https://x.com/NEI_pt; **TikTok:** www.tiktok.com/@noiteinvestigadores; **YouTube:** <https://www.youtube.com/@noitedosinvestigadores8383>) contents included "About us" posts, informative posts, interactive quizzes, and promotional videos. All content was designed to be accessible and engaging, emphasising the importance of science and research in everyday life. To keep content updated and on a consistent schedule, we planned monthly publications across all social media platforms, and prepared a diverse range of materials to guide partners and associate institutions on this implementation. The ERN social media channels were relaunched on July 22, with a series of posts introducing the updated brand image. These campaigns were designed to build momentum until the official announcement of ERN 2024. After this announcement, we developed a diverse range of posts that focused on presenting the event, the consortium, and the venues, as we aimed to attract new audiences who might not be familiar with the project. Additionally, we shared "Did You Know?" posts with topics related to the EU-Missions; trending topics integrated into promotional videos with countdowns, and recap posts covering both pre-events and the main event. The success of the social media campaigns was strengthened by the collaboration between ERN's social media and our partner venues' social channels.

The remaining channels were promoted both at a national and regional level to leverage regional partnerships and protocols established by each venue. This will be further explained throughout this report.

By following this structured process and aligning each step with our primary objectives, the 2024 project successfully engaged a wide range of audiences, inspired curiosity, and promoted a positive view of science and research across Portugal as well as of EU research funding programmes.

3. | Communication channels and strategies

3.1 | Brand image

The ERN visual identity was consistently applied across all communication platforms throughout the project. Therefore, it is important to describe it before providing an overview of these platforms.

In 2024, ERN’s visual identity was inspired by the previous project image (2021 edition). After a few years of visual stability, the graphic identity underwent a profound revamping in 2021 to reflect a more streamlined consortium and mobilisation capabilities of the public. Given the extensive overhaul to which our ERN’s image was subjected, the visual identity for ERN 2024/25 was carefully refined to highlight the updates while preserving key elements of the 2021 design.

The refreshed visual identity introduces a vibrant, modern look that is both professional and approachable, designed to engage a wide range of audiences. The updated logo combines geometric shapes with meaningful icons representing the EU-Missions and contrasting colours (Yellow: #ffdb00; Purple: #5c406c). The typeface Poppins is used for all ERN communications, ensuring readability and aligning with the modern feel of the brand - Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Left: ERN 21 brand identity. Right: ERN 24/25 brand identity.

To ensure that ERN visual identity was consistently upheld across all venues and partners, we developed a comprehensive visual identity manual. This manual was further supported by a general communication guidelines document, which included essential elements such as the financial statement, designated hashtags, ERN social media accounts to mention when sharing content on partners’ platforms, and tailored recommendations for post types best suited to each communication channel. To streamline the adoption process, we also included a printable checklist, enabling

partners to easily verify compliance with the guidelines at a glance.

3.2 | Overview of channels used

The multi-channel approach employed by the ERN project was designed to reach a diverse audience across Portugal, leveraging multiple communication platforms such as:

ERN website

The website is a crucial tool to communicate, promote and organise project activities and serves as the project's central information hub. Just like in the last edition, consortium partners decided to lodge the website in Ciência Viva's server, given its capacity to manage several websites at once and a dedicated IT team to match incoming demands, allowing us to save time and costs.

The website's structure is quite simple and straightforward, of which we share a few features below – Figure 2:

- The **homepage** features a visually appealing banner with the logo, event date, venues and a promotional video.
- There is an **About** page (“Sobre”) with a brief description of the event's history, objectives, and mission. Another page, **Partners** (“Parceiros”) contains information about the consortium institutions. Additionally, there is a **Contact Us** page (“Contacte-nos”) that presents visitors with the opportunity to contact the organisation, as well as with a call to action to follow our social media accounts.
- The **Venues** page (“Locais”) lists all event venues, each linking to a dedicated page with venue details, a link to the venue's website, and logos of sponsors and participating entities. Close to the event date, each venue displayed its programme in its page.
- The **Education** page (“Educação”) provides access to all the programmes under the “Researchers at schools” (WP3) activities. A dropdown menu includes sections for: Meet the Scientist, Participatory Debates, Programme for Social Inclusion through Science, and Youth Ambassadors Program.
- The **EU-Corner** page highlights the role of the European Union in funding research. It includes an EU-Corner promotional video, funding programmes sponsored by the European Union, and details on European projects that integrated ERN's events across the country.
- Finally, the **Press page** (“Imprensa”) contains a comprehensive list of press articles and TV/audio reports.
- Prior to the main event, pre-event information was featured in the homepage of the website. In this way, it was easy to understand what was going to happen right when accessing the page. Once the pre-event was over, each of them could be found in the main page of the corresponding venue.

Figure 2: Website menu structure.

Social networks

Social media platforms like Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and TikTok are key tools for science communication due to their wide reach and ease of sharing information. Given their role as major information channels, they are essential for promoting ERN activities while also combating misinformation by ensuring accuracy. Each platform features tailored posts, with some common themes and formats across channels. By leveraging the unique capabilities of each platform, we were able to reach diverse demographics and adapt our messaging to maximise engagement.

• Instagram

Our Instagram account, @noitedosinvestigadores, played a crucial role in visually engaging our audience and promoting the ERN events. The platform allowed us to use a dynamic mix of posts and stories, showcasing both informative and interactive content tailored to foster curiosity and excitement about science.

After the relaunch on 22 of July, the Instagram account shifted to reflect the refreshed visual identity, reflecting a diverse range of content, each serving a different purpose. Instagram content included:

1. **Brand relaunch and new visual identity:** the first posts introduced the updated ERN brand, featuring the new logo, colours and a sleek design aesthetic. These posts aimed to familiarise the audience with the new look and feel of ERN 2024/25. Prior to these posts, we shared two engaging stories: one featured a video with a dynamic colour transition, and the other asked for the audience's opinion on what exciting announcement was coming – Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Left: Feed image to showcase the identity transition. Middle: Official announcement of ERN new edition. Right: Instagram story that helped build buzz prior to the official announcement.

2. **Promoting activities posts:** A significant portion of the content focused on promoting upcoming pre-events and providing recaps. All pre-events were shared through Instagram Stories, using a consistent format that included the date, time, location (with venue details), the event title, and a link to access more information or a registration form, when applicable. All stories related

to pre-events were compiled into a profile highlight, making them easily accessible to everyone - Figure 4. After each pre-event, the associated venue shared recap images, which were reposted on the ERN account through Instagram Stories or as part of the "That's How It Happened" ("Foi Assim que Aconteceu") series of posts - Figure 5.

Figure 4 - Left: Pre-event story template. Right: Profile highlights.

Figure 5 - Example of the "That's how it happened" posts.

3. Informative posts: A wide range of informative posts were shared on ERN's Instagram account. We began by introducing the theme for the ERN 2024 edition - 5 EU-Missions, with a video showcasing each mission's name and icon. This was followed by "Did you Know?" ("Sabias que?") posts, one dedicated to each EU-Mission - Figure 6. These posts were interspersed with "Venue ERN" (Local NEI) series, where we highlighted one venue per post, describing its main field of research, key activities, and other distinctive information. We started by presenting the consortium partners, followed by the remaining associated venues. Additionally, we shared a story mentioning each venue's profile and compiled them into a highlight for easy access. Also, we shared a post featuring images from the previous edition, aiming the audience's memories and build excitement for the upcoming event - Figure 7.

Figure 6 - Left: video presenting the EU-Missions. Middle: example of the “Venue ERN” post. Right (2 stories): instagram story presenting ERN Venues.

Figure 7 - Example of “Did you Know” post.

4. Trending topics posts: One of the key Instagram posts we created responded to a real-time event: an earthquake that occurred in Portugal. As the topic was trending and important for public safety, we seized the opportunity to inform and educate our audience on what to do in the event of an earthquake. The post provided clear, science-based advice on earthquake preparedness, covering actions to take before, during and after such an event. It also highlighted the scientific reasoning behind these safety measures, reinforcing ERN’s commitment to promoting science literacy in real-world contexts – Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Example of a key post.

5. Program highlights: We promoted the event programmes through a carousel post. Each slide provided a glimpse into the unique activities planned at each venue, offering followers a snapshot of what to expect at their local event.

6. Event countdown videos: Leading up to the main ERN event, a series of countdown video posts were shared, building anticipation and reminding

followers of the upcoming dates. The countdown began with “One month left until ERN” video, which combined promotion with an explanatory segment. One week before the event, we posted an Instagram story featuring a countdown and a summary of the activities planned for the main event. Two days before the event, we incorporated trending content by filming ourselves placing ERN stickers in various locations, under the slogan “Every path leads to ERN” – Figure 9. On the event day, we shared an Instagram story with a countdown reading “Zero days left until ERN. It’s today!”. After the event, we shared all the stories in which we were mentioned and compiled them into a highlight titled “2024 Edition” (“Edição 2024”) – Figure 10.

Figure 9 – Example of “Every path leads to ERN” video post.

Figure 10 – Example of ERN countdown post.

7. Posts in collaboration: To further broaden our reach and foster community engagement, we leveraged partnerships to create collaborative content. These collaborations helped us tap into new audiences and enhance the overall visibility of ERN – Figure 11. In partnership with Associação CAIS, we organised a giveaway on Instagram, offering four notebooks from their “CAIS Recicla” collection. The mission of Associação CAIS is to contribute to the global improvement of living conditions for socially and economically vulnerable people, facing deprivation, exclusion or risk. By offering an incentive through a recognised local organisation, we encouraged audience participation, increased follower engagement, and supported a social cause linked to sustainability and social inclusion. Additionally, we collaborated with “Agenda Cultural do Porto” to create a promotional video aimed at raising awareness

of the upcoming ERN event. This video, highlighting the main aspects of the ERN project, included a call to action to visit the event in Porto and other venues, was shared on both our platforms and theirs (70K followers), extending our reach to their established audience.

Figure 11 - Example of a collaboration post.

8. Interactive content: To engage our audience in a dynamic and informative way, we used Instagram Stories to create interactive quizzes focused on key topics related to the EU Missions. These quizzes were designed to both educate and entertain, encouraging followers to test their knowledge on important scientific and environmental issues. These contents consisted of two “Do you know or not?” quizzes, two “Fact or Myth” quizzes and a “Who is Who” quiz – Figure 11 and 12.

Figure 11 - Example of a “Fact or Myth” post.

9. Commemorative days: To align with our educational mission and raise awareness of important societal and health-related issues, we created Instagram Stories on various commemorative days, such as World Lung Cancer Day and World Mental Health Day. These stories provided valuable information related to the theme of each day, including facts, prevention tips, and the scientific relevance of these health challenges. Some of these posts were made in collaboration with the i3S Instagram account as their researchers develop research concerning these topics. All the commemorative day stories were later compiled into a profile highlight, ensuring they remain accessible for followers to revisit and share – Figure 12.

Figure 12 – Example of “World Mental Health Day” post.

10. Recap video: Following the main event, we produced and shared a recap video to showcase the best moments from ERN 24. This video served as a dynamic summary of the event, capturing highlights, audience engagement, and the diverse range of activities held across various venues – Figure 13.

Figure 13 – Example of a Recap Video.

Taking everything into consideration, the ERN Instagram account has successfully relaunched its visual identity and focused on delivering content that is both engaging and informative. By using a mix of promotional posts, interactive stories, and consistent branding, the platform has built anticipation for the 2024/25 event while ensuring that followers remain engaged with science-related content.

- **Facebook**

As far as the ERN’s Facebook account is concerned, despite maintaining a significant follower base, we observed that engagement on the platform was notably lower compared to that of other social media channels. This trend aligns with the broader decline in Facebook’s active engagement rates, particularly with younger demographics, who have shifted towards more interactive platforms like Instagram and TikTok. Considering this, to ensure we maintained a presence on Facebook without dedicating excessive resources to creating platform-specific content, we opted for a synchronised content strategy. All content from our Instagram Stories was automatically synchronised with Facebook Stories, ensuring that the same interactive, educational, and promotional content was shared across both platforms seamlessly.

For Facebook posts, we primarily adapted content originally created for Instagram. This included adjusting post formats to better fit Facebook's layout and audience preferences. We also revised the post descriptions to better suit our Facebook followers, who tend to respond more positively to detailed and formal descriptions, compared to the shorter, more casual style used on Instagram. Additionally, we took advantage of Facebook's ability to include links in post descriptions, directing the audience to our website, YouTube videos, and other resources.

Additionally, after the event we created a photo album for each venue. These albums offered an immersive look into the various activities, demonstrations, and audience interactions across different venues. The albums - Figure 14 - provided a more structured way to share event highlights and allowed followers to engage with the content at their own pace.

Figure 14 - Facebook albums.

Due to the lower engagement rates observed on Facebook, we decided that creating a dedicated event on the platform, as initially planned, was not worth the time and resources. Instead, we suggested that each venue promote the event on the platform that best suited their audience and communication goals. For example, i3S chose to create their dedicated event on LinkedIn, where it gathered significant attention and engagement. This approach allowed venues to leverage the platforms their target audiences were most active, ensuring more effective outreach and better event promotion overall.

We acknowledged Facebook's declining engagement rates and for that reason we focused less on creating exclusive content for this platform. Instead, we used it as a secondary distribution channel, allowing us to reach an older audience segment that still actively used the platform without requiring extensive additional content production efforts.

- **X (formerly twitter)**

On X, our main goal was to grow our presence, considering this platform is the one with the smallest following. To do so, we aimed to leverage the platform's real-time communication capabilities to promote ERN, share updates and engage with our audiences, using concise and engaging content. Our content included:

1. Official event announcements and updates: We used X to announce the return of ERN and share important updates about the event and its activities. This helped us build anticipation and provide ongoing information in the lead-up to the main event.

2. Real-time commentary adaptation: While we did not provide real-time commentary during the event and pre-events, we ensured the feed remained active and relevant by reposting content from participants, partners, and venues who were involved in the pre-events and the main event. The large number of pre- and simultaneous events made it difficult for our team to produce real-time, high-quality commentary on each one. Thus, this strategy allowed us to maintain an up-to-date presence on the platform, fostering engagement without requiring continuous commentary.
3. Educational content with EU-mission focus: Instead of creating detailed threads as initially planned, we shared posts with images (adapted format from Instagram) that explained relevant concepts from the EU-Missions. These posts included links to the official EU websites for deeper exploration of the missions, ensuring our followers had access to comprehensive and reliable information.
4. Cross-platform sharing: We emphasised cross-platform sharing, in particular by directing users to the ERN website through relevant posts. This helped drive traffic to our website, where more detailed information about the event, the consortium, and the venues is available.
5. Hashtag strategy: We carefully selected short, relevant and trending hashtags to maximise the reach of our posts. This included both general hashtags related to science, research and education, as well as those specifically determined in the communication plan.
6. Partner and participant engagement: One of the most successful strategies was reposting content from our partners and participants, which helped us amplify the voices of those involved in ERN activities. This not only filled our feed with diverse content but also promoted our account to a wider audience. Additionally, this strengthened collaboration between partners, creating an effective communication chain.

- **YouTube**

YouTube plays a key role in our strategy to visually document and archive the ERN content. We use the platform to showcase past and current activities, ensuring that videos are easily accessible to a broad audience. Below are the strategies we implemented:

1. Playlists for content organisation: To ensure easy navigation and content filtering, we created a series of playlists based on event editions. These playlists allowed viewers to explore ERN's activities across different years in a structured manner. This approach not only made it easier for audiences to locate videos but also showcase the continuity of the project over time.
2. Event videos: We shared an event presentation video, introducing ERN 2024 and outlining key objectives, themes and activities. Also, we shared a video promoting the EU-Corner and EU funding programmes. These were designed to build anticipation for the event and offer a clear overview of what participants could expect, helping to engage a wider audience. After the event, we produced a recap video summarising the highlights from the main event.

This video showcased key moments, participant reactions, and a variety of activities that took place, giving both attendees and those who missed the event an overview of its success.

3. Live broadcast challenges: Although we initially planned to stream live events on the ERN YouTube channel, technical challenges prevented us from doing so. However, many regional venues hosted live broadcasts on their individual YouTube channels. This allowed some degree of event accessibility and visibility, even if not centralised.

Despite the challenges with live streaming, YouTube remained an essential part of our communication strategy, offering a comprehensive video archive of past events and evidencing the ongoing success and development of ERN over the years.

- **TikTok**

TikTok was a key addition to our communication strategy, providing a platform to engage a younger and more diverse audience through short, dynamic videos. Although we launched the ERN TikTok account later than planned, on 29 August, we made effective use of the platform to promote event-related content and build momentum in the lead-up to the ERN.

1. Late start and quick adaptation: Due to time constraints, we were only able to start the TikTok account at the end of August, which limited the time we had to establish the platform. However, we quickly adapted by focusing primarily on promotional content to drive awareness of the upcoming event.
2. Content strategy: We created short, engaging promotional videos, including event countdowns, venue highlights, and videos combining images and videos from previous editions. In all cases, we focused on trending topics and video formats to tailor our content and boost our TikTok account's visibility.
3. Cross-platform promotion: Since the ERN TikTok account had been recently created, it was important to drive followers from our other platforms to this one. To do so, we shared our TikTok account on Instagram and Facebook Stories, along with the content as it was published.

Despite the limited time available for TikTok content creation, the platform proved valuable for generating visually engaging and highly shareable content, enhancing ERN 2024's promotional efforts. While building a strong following takes time, our initial presence laid a solid foundation for future growth, showing TikTok's potential as a key channel for connecting with younger, more digital active audiences in the next edition.

Media

While social media played a crucial role in reaching our audiences, traditional media were essential to extending our reach and ensuring visibility across different demographic groups. Our approach to media outreach involved strategic coordination at

both the national and regional levels, allowing us to maximise the impact of our message through various outlets, including newspapers, television, and online platforms.

To support media partners and encourage coverage of the event, we prepared a press kit. The kit included:

- Press releases: A national press release was prepared and distributed to relevant media outlets, offering an engaging overview of ERN 2024, its objectives, and key activities. Additionally, a regional press release template was created and sent to the associated venues, allowing them to adapt and share it with local media outlets and partners [Annex - Press releases].
- Sponsor kit: We developed a sponsor kit that was sent to potential sponsors and suppliers at both national and regional levels. This included information on sponsorship and support opportunities, detailing how sponsors could gain exposure across ERN's media channels and communication platforms [Annex - Sponsor kit].
- Visual materials: All relevant materials such as the event's branding materials, logos, and banners were sent to associate partners, venues, media and others to ensure consistency in media coverage [Annex - Visual materials].

To maximise the impact of our media promotion, we implemented the following strategies:

- Invitations: We prepared and sent invitations to a diverse range of audiences, including: researchers and academic institutions, local community leaders and organisations, media outlets and digital influencers. One of these influencers was Carolina Guedes Andrade, a digital influencer based in Porto, who promoted ERN in her Instagram stories by sharing our content. She also attended the main event in Porto on September 27, where she provided coverage of the event on her Instagram and TikTok accounts. Carolina's counts with 27,3K followers on her Instagram account and 285K followers on her TikTok account.
- Media partners: One of our main objectives was to establish a partnership with a broadcaster to ensure that ERN gained high-level visibility through TV or radio channels. Even though this was only possible at a regional level, as part of our media strategy we developed a Mrec - "Medium Rectangle ad", published on Público - a Portuguese daily national newspaper based in Lisbon. The Mrec included key information such as event date, and directed the users to the ERN website. Due to challenges in securing radio coverage, we opted to promote ERN through the podcast Alegria de Viver, a portuguese podcast with more than 2000 listeners per episode. A member of the communication team (Rute Verdade) discussed the project as a whole, the event objectives, key activities and the importance of science engagement, effectively amplifying our message and attracting interest from potential attendees.

Offline promotion

To effectively promote the ERN event offline, we implemented a range of strategies aimed at reaching diverse audiences and maximising visibility. These strategies were executed at a national level whenever possible, while also incorporating significant local efforts. To this end, a diverse range of materials (Figure 15) were developed and shared across all venues. These materials included:

- A3 poster
- MUPI
- Roll-up
- Invites
- Postcards
- Program template

Figure 15 - Left: Program; Middle: A3 poster; Right: Powerpoint template.

Additionally, all venues received brand identity guidelines, including logos, colours and typography, enabling them to develop materials tailored to their specific space and event, always in line with the visual identity manual.

Regional communication efforts

The promotion of the ERN event across various regions involved a comprehensive mix of digital, print and broadcast media strategies. Each venue tailored its communication efforts to effectively reach local audiences, while keeping the alignment with the overarching ERN brand identity. Below are the key communications approaches implemented by the different venues:

- Social media campaigns: All venues utilised platforms like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, X, and YouTube to engage with their local communities. The social media campaigns included regular posts, event countdowns, and promotional videos that highlighted key aspects of the ERN event, driving traffic to event pages and increasing engagement. The collaboration between venues was crucial because when partners shared posts featuring the ERN identity to promote their events and programs, it significantly enhanced our collective visibility and reinforced a unified brand message, which helps clarify the consortia's involved venues and partners. By leveraging each venue's audience, we were able to amplify our communication efforts and create a more cohesive promotional narrative.
- Newsletters and websites: Newsletters were a crucial part of the communication strategy, allowing venues to directly inform their audience about upcoming activities and provide event updates. The official ERN website, as well as individual venue websites, were regularly updated with relevant information, ensuring easy access to event details.
- Press releases and media coverage: Press releases were sent to both regional and national media outlets, securing coverage in newspapers, TV channels, and local

news websites. Some venues achieved television exposure on channels like CMTV, as well as radio interviews on stations like M80, broadening the event's reach.

- Local partnerships and collaborations: Collaborations with local municipalities, such as the Municipalities of Vila Nova de Foz Côa and Oeiras, played a key role in promoting the event. These partnerships helped integrate ERN promotion into municipal websites, social media platforms, and local initiatives, such as street signage and community engagement efforts.
- Outdoor advertising: Several venues resorted to banners, MUPIs, video banners at roundabouts, and outdoor screens to maximise visibility in public spaces. This offline promotion effectively complemented the digital campaigns and expanded the event's awareness to a broader audience.
- Merchandising and printed materials: Venues distributed flyers, posters and branded merchandise, such as tote bags, pens, coasters in local bars and restaurants, and bracelets featuring EU-Missions, to further enhance event promotion. These materials ensured that the event remained visible and accessible to local communities.
- Event listings and regional agendas: Many venues leveraged local event platforms and regional agendas, such as "Event Regional Agenda" to list ERN and boost attendance. These listings provided an additional promotional layer that targeted audiences actively seeking events in the area.

Altogether, these regional communication efforts ensured that ERN reached a wide and diverse audience, effectively promoting both the event and the importance of science communication in local communities.

4. | Metrics and evaluation

This section provides an overview of the metrics collected across multiple domains to assess the project's impact, identify success, and guide improvements for future editions. By monitoring various indicators, we aimed to measure the effectiveness of our communication strategies, audience engagement, and media presence.

4.1 | Digital platforms analytics

As previously discussed, digital platforms are a fundamental tool in the ERN communication strategy. To understand the effectiveness of our strategies, it is essential to analyse metrics from both the ERN website and social media channels. By analysing these metrics, we can gain valuable insights into user behaviour, content performance, and the reach of our messaging.

4.1.1 | Website

The analysis of the ERN 2024 website performance reveals crucial insights regarding user behaviour, engagement levels, and areas for improvement.

The landing page, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/>, received a substantial amount of traffic, recording 4,300 visitors and 20,200 pageviews. Nevertheless, this is somewhat misleading, as this page serves as both the landing page and a collection point for other sections of the website. Therefore, it is challenging to ascertain user interactions with specific content elements, such as the list of venues, which is vital for understanding engagement levels. The bounce rate for this landing page stands at 38%, suggesting that while many visitors are entering the site, a significant portion is not engaging with the content presented. This indicates a potential need for improved navigation or more engaging introductory content that encourages visitors to scroll down and explore further.

The About page, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/sobre>, had 418 visitors with a higher bounce rate of 64%, indicating possible disinterest or confusion regarding the content presented. Similarly, the Partners page, <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/parceiros>, recorded 190 visitors with a bounce rate of 40%. While the latter has a smaller bounce rate, it is still important to optimise both pages, as they contain essential information about our mission, values, and partners that underpin our project. Engaging our audience with our objectives is crucial, especially given the existence of other consortia in Portugal.

The pages under the Education menu deliver the correct information but require enhancements to the user experience in order to reduce the bounce rate. These pages present a diverse number of hyperlinks that require graphical improvement to become more aesthetically appealing and interactive.

This website was adapted from the 2021 edition, and its design and development primarily took place at the onset of this edition's preparation. As a result, many of these issues were identified prior to the ERN 2024 main event. However, due to the short timeframe and intense workload, along with the necessity of maintaining an accessible

website during this critical period of the project, we opted to gather insights and feedback during the event and then address these challenges. This year, we will focus on making the necessary changes and adaptations to improve user experience in order to achieve an improved result by the 2025 edition. This reformulation will be carried out in close collaboration between the communication team (i3S) and the hosting website team (Ciência Viva).

Despite all the issues identified, the overall performance presents a strong foundation for future improvements. The substantial visitor numbers indicate a keen interest in the content and an effective outreach strategy. The commitment to ongoing improvement reflects our dedication to fostering a vibrant community around the ERN initiatives, ensuring that we can better serve our audience and fulfil our mission in the coming edition.

4.1.1.1. | Reformulation plan

As part of our strategy to improve the overall user experience and make our website more intuitive, we plan to change the menu bar. By updating it, we intend to ensure smoother navigation and greater clarity. The current structure, while functional, can be optimised to better reflect the breadth of our content and make key sections more accessible. Our main objective is to address the issues highlighted by user feedback, which indicates that some sections on the website are difficult to locate, especially event programmes, leading to higher bounce rates on important pages. Initially, we chose to use a Linktree to consolidate links to each venue's programme, making information more accessible. In the long term, we plan to restructure the menu bar, with dropdown sections, which will make it easier for users to find the information they are seeking, decreasing confusing situations, and enhancing engagement.

Figure 16 describes the proposed menu structure.

Key changes include:

Figure 16 - Proposed menu structure.

- Change the name of the "Start" (Início) section to "The ERN" (A NEI) and compress all the "About us" and "Partners" information into a dropdown menu.
- The "Venue" section (Locais) will include all venues associated with our project, providing direct links to each location page. This not only increases accessibility but also helps users find the information they need. Additionally, by setting these as distinct website pages, we will have clearer access to these pages' statistics.
- Addition of the "Pre-events" (Pré-eventos) and the "Programme" ("Programa") menu sections. These will display very clearly all the pre-events happening and each venue's main event programme.
- Addition of the "Resources" menu section. Here we will include a subsection named "EU Resources" (Recursos UE) and another named "ERN Resources" (Recursos NEI). All

the educational and interactive resources developed in the scope of ERN activities will be available under the “ERN Resources” section. Similarly to the previous edition, some educational resources developed by the EU will be displayed in the “EU Resources” section.

In addition to restructuring the website’s menu for improved navigation, we are planning to change the website domain, currently <https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/>, to better align with how users typically search for information about the ERN. Data and user behaviour show that people rarely search for the event under its acronym (NEI – in Portuguese). Instead, they are more likely to search for “European Researchers Night”. By changing the domain to reflect the event’s full name (for example <https://noiteuropeiainvestigadores.cienciaviva.pt>), we increase the chances of appearing higher in search engine results and attracting relevant traffic to the website.

Finally, we aim to enhance the website’s overall graphic design and user experience. The focus of this reformulation is to create a more visually appealing, engaging, and user-friendly interface that encourages visitors to explore the content, improving both usability and engagement. Changes will include:

- Footer redesign: The objective is to maintain the information currently presented in the footer (Partner logos, funding statement, and social media icons) but rearrange how they are presented in order to fit in more smoothly with the remaining pages – Figure 17.

Figure 17 – Proposed footer structure.

- Colour sections to segment the homepage: In the current website, the heavy use of pure white makes the design flat and can be overwhelming to the user. To address this we will introduce coloured sections to visually segment the content. These sections will toggle between ERN purple and white. To complement this we plan to adapt the text format to better fit these changes.
- Text layout: The existing layout places too much content in large, single-column blocks, which can be hard to read, waning the user’s interest. Thus, we will limit each line to no more than 12 words to improve readability. Additionally, we will structure the content in two columns, creating a more balanced layout and enhancing text flow.
- Highlights feature: We plan to create a dedicated “Highlights” feature (Destaques) on the homepage that showcases images from past events, upcoming events, key announcements or any other relevant content. This adds a more interactive feature in the website where users can easily access relevant information.
- Interactive buttons and boxes: Currently, the website is mostly static and lacks interactive elements to keep users engaged. By introducing buttons and content boxes that prompt user actions, we offer a better user experience, ultimately reducing website bounce rate. These features might include interactive lists, theme

cards and call to action boxes.

The website reformulation as described, will help improve both usability and visual appeal, aligning the online presence of the project with ERN's objectives.

4.1.2 | Social media

Regarding the evaluation of social media analytics for the ERN 2024 project, we focused on performance metrics across our primary platforms: Instagram, Facebook, X, YouTube and TikTok. Each platform offers unique insights into audience engagement, allowing us to assess the impact of our communication strategies. Across all platforms, the data correspond to the period between **July 22 and October 10**.

Instagram analytics

Instagram successfully reached **10600** accounts, the vast majority (93.7%) non-followers, aligning with ERN's followers base of **948**. The platform effectively attracted a broader audience beyond the existing followers, demonstrating that the content strategy broke out of ERN's immediate network and engaged a wider public, a key goal for increasing awareness and outreach.

During this period, the account experienced a growth rate of **36.9%**, gaining **+256** new followers (from 692 to 948). This growth is notable and nearly reached the goal set for both editions (1000 followers). Nevertheless, there is room for improvement in converting the substantial number of new viewers into followers. Stronger conversion strategies such as end reels and stories with a follow prompt or inserting more direct calls-to-action in the copy, could further boost the number of followers.

Published content varied between **27 posts, 131 stories and 4 reels**, each format performing differently:

- Reels performed exceptionally well in terms of reach, with **6614** accounts reached through just four reels, showing that short-form video content is highly favoured by Instagram's algorithm and audience.
- Posts reached **5263** accounts, illustrating that static images and carrousels remain effective, though less so than video content.
- Stories also garnered substantial reach, with **4278** accounts reached.

The top five pieces of content, in terms of reach, included 2 reels (August 27 and September 25) followed by 2 posts (September 24 and August 26) and a story (September 27). In addition, while it was not first published on the ERN account, it is important to note that the reel published in collaboration with "Agenda Cultural do Porto" reached a total of 4460 accounts, with nearly 100 users engaging by either linking or saving the post.

The platform achieved 307 engaged accounts, with engagement coming mostly from posts. This reveals that, while videos and stories reached a broader audience, traditional posts were more effective in driving active interaction. Engagement peaked on certain posts, with high numbers of likes, saves and comments, and profile visits:

- August 26 post: 67 likes, 20 saves, 23 profile visits. This post converted into 6 news follows. The post covers the earthquake topic, which supports the decision of implementing a content strategy based on trending topics.
- September 27 post: 66 likes, 171 comments, 1 save, 10 profile visits. This post converted into 14 new follows. The post consisted of a giveaway (in collaboration with CAIS Association) designed to promote engagement, which once more proved to be an effective strategy.

In the dedicated period, 2213 profile visits and 120 external link taps were registered, suggesting that the content successfully directed traffic to external resources and prompted further exploration of the ERN profile.

These metrics underline the importance of using a diverse mix of content, as reels, for instance, seem to appeal more to younger, non-following audiences, while posts and stories resonate more with existing followers or those looking for more in-depth information.

A detailed breakdown of the audience demographics highlights:

- Location: 91,6% of the audience was from Portugal, reflecting the national focus of the project.
- Cities: Engagement was highest in Lisbon (14,3%) followed by Coimbra (7,5%) and Porto (7,4%). In general, these results align with the most impactful regions of the event, with the Lisbon area hosting the two largest venues, followed by Porto. However, it is notable that Coimbra, where no ERN event was organised by this consortium, showed significant engagement. This suggests that confusion among the general public about the different consortia in Portugal persists despite efforts to counter it in previous editions. For the 2025 edition, we are considering a more straightforward strategy to address this challenge.
- Age and Gender: Our audience skewed towards a younger demographic, with the majority aged between 25–34 years old (33,4%) and 35–44 years old (25,8%). Additionally, 72,1% of the audience is female, suggesting that the messaging or topics may resonate more with women and young adults.
- Concluding this analysis, we can state that Instagram was a highly effective tool for expanding ERN's reach. The varied performance of reels, posts and stories underscores the importance of a multi-format strategy tailored to both reach and engagement goals.

Facebook analytics

Despite challenges, Facebook remained a key platform for communicating with the ERN audience. The metrics reflect how well the platform supported outreach efforts, particularly to connect with an older demographic and maintain visibility. During the period considered, a total of **6000** accounts were reached. Notably, there were **2800** profile visits, which indicates a solid interest in the ERN brand, as nearly half of the reached audience took the initiative to explore the page further. However, the interaction rate of approximately **8,75%** (525 interactions) is modest, suggesting that while the

content is attracting attention, there is space to improve user participation. The follower count of 5152 (+58) reflects a stable and loyal audience base.

In terms of content creation, similarly to Instagram, a total of 25 posts were made. The audience demographic shows a significant concentration in Portugal (91,6%), with Lisbon being the most represented city. This aligns with ERN's goals, though there is potential for broader regional outreach.

Considering Facebook's current landscape, these metrics meet realistic expectations, though there is always room for improvement. We will continue to focus on video and interactive posts, along with clear calls-to-action, to boost engagement.

X analytics

The transition from Twitter to X has led to significant changes in platform functionality, limiting the availability of detailed analytics. Despite these constraints, the available data provides valuable insights.

During the considered period, the account achieved **8,263** impressions, reflecting the total number of times content appeared in users' feeds. This demonstrates that ERN content had visibility within the X ecosystem. The platform's algorithm, which tends to favour short-form content, was effectively utilised, particularly with posts relating to trending topics and event-related announcements.

The total of **55** retweets suggests that users were willing to engage and amplify the content. However, as we aim to grow our presence on X, we might need to adjust the content to feature more shareable and relatable posts, such as intriguing facts, or real-time event updates. One challenge is the lack of partner support on the platform, as many associated venues do not have X accounts. The cross-promotion and retweets of key partners is a strategy we plan to enhance throughout the year, aiming for a more impactful presence during the 2025 edition of ERN.

The account increased to **105** followers, demonstrating that ERN content is drawing some attention, though perhaps not as quickly as anticipated.

In summary, the performance of the ERN campaign on X (formerly Twitter) was stable, but there is significant room for growth. Continued efforts will focus on leveraging X's real-time communication strengths, especially during event peaks, and growing the follower base through active participation in trending conversation relevant to ERN's goals.

YouTube analytics

For ERN 2024, our YouTube strategy was somewhat limited compared to other platforms, as technical and strategic decisions led to live streaming responsibilities being transferred to individual venues. As a result, only **3** videos were uploaded to the central ERN YouTube channel. These videos served as supporting content to complement the website, where a significant portion of the audience viewed them.

The first video garnered the most attention, accumulating **111** views on YouTube itself, an additional **188** views were recorded through the website, highlighting the

significant role the website played in amplifying our content. The second and third video received less attention, even though the discrepancy between YouTube and Website views still underlines how important website embedding was to reach. Despite these limited uploads, our YouTube channel currently has **32** subscribers.

For the 2025 edition, we aim to centralise all video content and live streams on the official ERN YouTube Channel. This decision stems from the realisation that fragmented streaming across multiple venue-specific channels diluted our ability to capture broader audience engagement in a unified space. For instance, ITQB NOVA's event live stream reached 170 views, so a strong interest at the venue level clearly exists. By consolidating such streams on the ERN channel, we can capitalise on the attention, building a more substantial, cohesive audience and elevating the overall visibility of the event.

TikTok analytics

TikTok was a new addition to the ERN social media strategy, starting on 29 August 2024, which gave the team a fresh platform to reach younger, more diverse audiences. Despite the late start, the platforms show promising signs of engagement and growth potential, even still at an early stage.

The account managed to reach **3557** users, with **4487** video views across the eight videos posted. This level of video consumption demonstrates an audience's interest in the content and their willingness to engage with videos, which is the core strength of TikTok. Furthermore, there were **27** profile visits, indicating a decent level of curiosity from users who engaged with the content and wanted to learn more about ERN. The account accumulated **25** likes across the videos, which demonstrates early engagement. With more consistent posting and experimenting with trending TikTok formats, this metric could rise. Similarly, the account received 13 comments and 17 shares, which is an encouraging sign. Sharing is one of the most impactful forms of engagement on TikTok as it helps to expand organic reach.

The primary audience falls between **25-34 years old (54.2%)**, followed by **45-54 years old (37,5%)** and **18-24 years old (8,3%)**. Interestingly, the platform skewed toward a more mature audience than typical for TikTok, which often has a younger demographic. Future campaigns might focus on attracting the younger 18-24 demographic to balance the audience mix. The gender split was almost even, with **52% female and 48% male viewers**. This balance shows broad appeal across genders, a positive indicator for future content planning that doesn't need to overly target one demographic group over another.

With just **8** videos created, the engagement metrics and views are promising. TikTok is a platform where frequency and consistency matter, so increasing the volume of content is one of our objectives to achieve better results. The account attracted 10 followers, which reflects the early stage of the account. Even so, it has managed to generate moderate engagement. TikTok shows potential as a platform to engage audiences, but more consistent posting combined with trend-based content and interactive formats, will be crucial for future success.

Overall, the social media campaign effectively met its core objectives, successfully raising awareness of both the ERN 2024 and the EU-EMBRACES project. Through targeted

posts, interactive content, and platform-specific strategies, we reached over **32000** users across various platforms, engaging a diverse audience and maximising visibility within our key demographic segments. The campaign's broad reach and steady engagement rates indicate a well-executed approach to digital outreach, despite challenges such as platform transitions and initial audience-building on newer channels like TikTok.

4.2 | Media coverage

As aforementioned, media outlets were essential for the ERN 2024 strategy to broaden and ensure that the event reached a wide audience. The project gained significant traction across both national and regional outlets, with a total of 37 articles, reports and broadcasts referencing ERN 2024 [Annex 1 – Clipping list]. This is a testament to the widespread interest from various media channels.

- At a national level, 7 articles were published, ensuring broad visibility across Portugal. These national outlets played a crucial role in bringing ERN 2024 to the attention of the general public, particularly in urban centres and among those with a strong interest in science and research.
- At a regional level, several venues successfully garnered significant media attention. Notably, CCV Lagos achieved the highest media coverage with 10 articles. This reflects not only a strong local interest but also effective communication and promotion efforts. Table 2 summarises clipping data.

Venue	Number of articles
CCV Alviela	4
CCV Estremoz	-
CCV Braga	3
CCV Bragança	-
CCV Lagos	10
CCV Tavira	1
i3S	3
Museu do Côa	-
Pavilhão do Conhecimento	4
Oeiras – ITQB NOVA	5

Table 1. - Articles per venue.

Certain venues, such as CCV Estremoz, CCV Bragança and Museu do Côa, did not achieve any mentionable media coverage, as indicated by the lack of articles in the data. This underscores potential areas for improvement in engaging local media for the 2025 edition.

One of the national articles referring to ERN 2024 was published in *Público* on

September 27, providing an in-depth description of all venues and their activities. This article, featured in such a significant newspaper with more than **47000** paid subscriptions, gave ERN substantial visibility across the country and served as invaluable promotion for the project. Additionally, as mentioned earlier, ERN 2024 strategy included a Mrec Ad in the same newspaper. This advertisement helped boost national awareness of the event and while it does not directly reflect in the clipping count, the exposure generated by this ad was crucial in reinforcing ERN's presence in the national media landscape.

The Mrec ad campaign ran from September 24 to September 27, and generated a total of 127,420 impressions with 115 clicks, resulting in an overall click-through rate (CTR) of 0,09%. The daily breakdown is as follows:

Date	Ad server impressions	Ad server clicks	Ad server CTR
24/09/2024	16756	8	0,05%
25/09/2024	33242	26	0,08%
26/09/2024	52108	74	0,14%
27/09/2024	25314	7	0,02%
Total	127420	115	0,09%

Table 2. - Mrec ad campaign numbers.

The highest number of impressions occurred on September 26, which might correlate with the timing of related events or announcements made the day before the main event. The total of 115 clicks indicates audience engagement with the ad content. While the number may seem modest, the gradual increase in clicks over the first three days suggests that the ad gained traction, peaking with a CTR of 0,14%. The notable drop in clicks on September 27 could imply ad fatigue. Additionally, the article published in Público on this day may have contributed to this decline by providing the public with the information they needed about the project and the event, reducing necessity to search for more details or click through the ad.

The overall CTR of 0,09% falls below the industry benchmarks for display advertising, which typically range from 0,1% or 0,5%. This may indicate the need for optimization in ad design or targeting to better engage the audience.

As we reflect on this campaign, several strategies emerge for improvement. We should consider adjusting the duration of the ads, refining the content, and exploring different platforms for display. In particular, exploring targeted advertising options such as google ads could align more closely with our objectives and potentially yield engagement results. For the 2025 edition, we will adapt our strategies based on these insights, with the goal of enhancing and optimising our advertising efforts to engage our audience more effectively.

Overall, the Mrec camping illustrated the importance of monitoring performance

metrics to inform ongoing strategies. Although the average CTR across the campaign was relatively low, the substantial number of impressions reflects a significant level of visibility for the ERN project. As a whole, the media coverage achieved through media outlets, combined with targeted advertising efforts, contributed to build anticipation and excitement for the ERN event and promote the EU-Embraces project.

4.3 | Regional campaigns

Each venue used a mix of digital and physical promotional strategies, including social media posts, email newsletters, local advertisements, and partnerships. Venues aimed to raise awareness of ERN's events and attract participants from various demographic groups, from students to local families and professionals.

One of the most impactful regional campaigns was the strategic placement of outdoors ads by ITQB NOVA in partnership with *Câmara Municipal de Oeiras*. These advertisements were positioned in three high-traffic areas—Oeiras Parque (a major shopping centre), Carnaxide, and Paço de Arcos—reaching an estimated 180,000 people. Additionally, i3S promoted the event through various communication channels offered by the University of Porto (UP), including UP News, the UP newsletter, and the university's social media platforms. On average, UP News reaches 150,000 page views per month and the UP newsletter is distributed to 46,000 potential readers and subscribers. UP's social media channels have approximately 80,000 followers. Furthermore, the event was featured in the *Ciência et al* newsletter (i3S's educational outreach program), reaching an audience of 355 teachers. *Pavilhão do Conhecimento* also promoted the event on Pumpkin.pt, an event platform with over 500,000 subscribers, contributing to more than 90,000 people becoming aware of the ERN event through this campaign.

Many of the regional communication efforts are challenging to quantify in metrics. However, it's important to acknowledge the social media presence across the nine venues associated with this consortium. Below is the follower count for each venue on Instagram:

- CCV Alviela: 1446
- CCV Braga: 2093
- CCV Bragança: 1402
- CCV Estremoz: 1144
- ITQB NOVA: 2883
- i3S: 4688
- CCV Lagos: 1664
- Museu do Côa: 5675
- Pavilhão do Conhecimento: 20300

These follower bases play a crucial role in enhancing ERN's visibility, significantly expanding outreach and engagement at the local level. Below, we present the metrics

for selected Instagram posts shared by our partners, which illustrate the engagement and reach achieved through their collaborative support. To ensure consistency across the selected posts, we focused on the metrics for posts that showcased each venue's program, a format utilised by all venues:

- Pavilhão do Conhecimento shared a post on September 26, reaching a total of 1279 accounts. Out of these, 56 accounts actively engaged with the content (49 likes, 1 save and 6 shares) – Figure 18.

Figure 18 – Shared post – Pavilhão do Conhecimento.

- i3S shared a post on September 25, reaching a total of 1925 accounts. Out of these, 108 accounts engaged with the content (99 likes, 5 saves and 4 external link taps) – Figure 19.

Figure 19 – Shared post – i3S.

- ITQB NOVA shared a post on September 24, reaching a total of 1,545 accounts with 95 of these actively engaging with the content – Figure 20.

Figure 20- Shared post – ITQB Nova.

- CCV Bragança shared a post on September 25, reaching a total of 1432 accounts. Out of these, 30 accounts engaged with the content (29 likes and 1 save) – Figure 21.

Figure 21 – Shared post – CCV Bragança.

- CCV Braga shared a post on September 25, reaching a total of 241 accounts. Out of these, 13 accounts engaged with the content (12 likes and 1 external link tap) – Figure 22.

Figure 21 – Shared post – CCV Braga.

- CCV Alviela shared a post on September 24, reaching a total of 208 accounts. Out of these, 15 accounts engaged with the content (14 likes and 1 external link tap) – Figure 22.

Figure 22 – Shared post – CCV Alviela.

- CCV Estremoz shared a post on September 25, reaching a total of 63 accounts – Figure 23.

Figure 23 – Shared post – CCV Estremoz.

- Museu do Côa shared a post on September 27, reaching a total of 319 accounts. Out of these, 15 accounts engaged with the content – Figure 24.

Figure 24 – Shared post – Museu do Côa.

- CCV Lagos shared a post on September 18, reaching a total of 182 accounts. Out of these, 11 accounts engaged with the content (9 likes, 1 share and 1 save) – Figure 25.

Figure 24 – Shared post – CCV Lagos.

4.4 | Attendance and reach

The reach and attendance metrics provide a crucial measure of the overall success of the ERN 2024 awareness campaign. Pre-events served as key promotional tools and engagement boosters leading up to the main event, allowing us to create early momentum and build interest across different audience segments. Understanding how these communication efforts translated into attendance—both in the pre-events and the main event—helps us assess the effectiveness of our strategy in reaching and engaging target groups.

Table 3 summarises these data:

Local	Built-up activities	Participants (Built-up activities)	Participants (Main-event)
CCV Alviela	Activity 1	10	50
	Activity 2	18	
	Activity 3	30	
CCV Estremoz	Activity 1	205	207
	Activity 2	4447	

CCV Braga	Activity 1	7	213
	Activity 2	11	
	Activity 3	10	
CCV Bragança	Activity 1	200	100
	Activity 2	35	
	Activity 3	19	
CCV Lagos	Activity 1	7	43
	Activity 2	50	
	Activity 3	4	
I3S	Activity 1	15	400
	Activity 2	17000	
	Activity 3	12	
Museu do Côa	Activity 1	300	687
	Activity 2	50	
	Activity 3	48	
	Activity 4	10	
Pavilhão do Conhecimento	Activity 1	4000	1700
	Activity 2	300	
Oeiras (ITQB NOVA)	Activity 1	350	1500
	Activity 2	6	
	Activity 3	180	

Table 3 – Attendance and Reach.

In analysing the attendance and reach data, it is essential to recognise each venue's differing contexts, particularly the size and location of associated centres. Venues located in major urban areas, such as Pavilhão do Conhecimento, in Lisbon, or i3S, in Porto, naturally attracted higher numbers of participants, both during built-up activities and the main event. This reflects not only the larger population in these areas but also the established reputation and visibility of these institutions.

In contrast, venues located in smaller regions, such as CCV Alviela or CCV Lagos, understandably had lower attendance figures. However, considering their local populations and regional outreach, these numbers still reflect successful engagement with their communities. The communication strategy for these areas focused on local partnerships and community engagement, which was effective within the limits of their smaller populations. For instance, CCV Estremoz showed a strong performance with 4447 participants in one of its activities, which speaks to its successful target outreach and effective promotion in a smaller city context.

In terms of CCV Bragança and Museu do Côa, both of which are situated in more remote regions, the data shows a moderate but consistent level of engagement.

Museu do Côa attracted 687 participants during the main event, an impressive number for a less populated region. As an established and significant museum in Portugal, with hundreds of visitors each day, its strong visibility and communication efforts likely contributed to this high number of participants, despite the remote location.

Considering attendance levels, the pre-events were generally successful in generating interest and boosting attendance for the main event. The activities held prior to the main event, created momentum, particularly in the larger venues, where engagement numbers were significantly higher. Furthermore, the success of pre-events suggests that early communication efforts, including social media campaigns and community partnerships, effectively built anticipations for both pre-events and the main event. The varying level of attendance reflects the diverse nature of the associated venues and their respective audiences. Thus, the communication efforts were adapted to these different contexts, recognizing that larger venues could leverage more extensive social media and media outreach, while smaller venues need a more localised approach.

In summary, while attendance was naturally higher in more populous areas, the communication strategies effectively maximised reach relative to the size of each venue's community. By tailoring the approach to the regional contexts and leveraging both national and local communication channels, the ERN project was able to engage a broad and diverse audience across Portugal. The importance of adapting communication efforts to fit the venue size and regional characteristics is thus highlighted, ensuring that each venue was able to reach its potential in terms of audience engagement.

5. | Conclusion

The ERN 2024 awareness campaign achieved significant strides in reaching and engaging diverse audiences, despite the challenges encountered across digital platforms, media outreach, and the main event itself. Each element of the campaign played a unique role in building visibility, fostering participation, and connecting people with the mission of European Researchers' Night.

The performance on social media platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and X was instrumental in reaching a diverse range of audiences. Instagram, as our most engaged platform, successfully attracted a broad audience through a mix of posts, stories and reels, achieving noteworthy metrics in audience reach and engagement. Similarly, TikTok allowed us to explore a younger demographic with visually engaging, promotional content, while X provided an accessible, structured feed for updates and quick interactions. While Facebook's engagement was modest, it reinforced the need to leverage cross-platform synergies and evaluate platform-specific strategies moving forward. YouTube also presented both opportunities and limitations: while local venues conducted successful live streams, centralising these under ERN's primary account could help unify branding and increase audience retention in future editions.

Our website served as a crucial information hub, generating thousands of visits. The insights gained have identified areas where user experience and design enhancements can improve navigation and content accessibility, which will be valuable as we prepare for future events. These updates will address technical issues, and ensure consistent, visually appealing design that better serves our audience.

The comprehensive media and regional awareness campaign efforts successfully amplified the reach and visibility of ERN 2024, fostering engagement across diverse communities. Through strategic partnerships with media outlets and targeted outreach via local campaigns, we maximised our impact by tailoring content to regional audiences while reinforcing a unified ERN identity. Media outlets extended our national reach, with targeted advertisements, press releases, and key media partnerships establishing a strong presence in both traditional and digital spaces. Meanwhile, regional campaigns by our partner venues contributed to deeper engagement by promoting ERN activities through locally relevant channels and audiences.

Overall, ERN 2024 multi-channel strategy proved effective in extending reach and facilitating access to event information across various platforms. With a commitment to refining these strategies and acting on collecting feedback, the ERN team believes that we are well-positioned to enhance the visibility, engagement and overall experience in the 2025 campaign. Each insight gathered from this year's campaign serves as a foundation for a stronger approach that will bring ERN closer to its community, sparking curiosity and connection with scientific discovery.

ANNEX

European Researchers' Night 2024/2025

Communication Report D1.2. Awareness Campaign 2024

1. | Press Releases

A national press release was prepared and distributed to relevant media outlets, offering an engaging overview of ERN 2024, its objectives, and key activities. Additionally, a regional press release template was created and sent to the associated venues, allowing them to adapt and share it with local media outlets and partners.

Nota de imprensa

Para divulgação imediata

Noite de festa da Ciência em todo o país

Admirar as estrelas, participar em *escape rooms*, identificar rochas, crustáceos, bivalves e corais, passear de barco, voar como uma águia, visitar o mundo das abelhas, experimentar simuladores de condução, degustar um menu com «pegada reduzida» e criar uma orquestra de sons são apenas algumas das atividades da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores. E isto é só uma amostra de uma vasta programação que promete surpreender e envolver o público em experiências imersivas de ciência e tecnologia. Está pronto para aceitar o desafio e entrar no fascinante mundo da investigação científica?

A 27 de setembro, a Ciência volta a sair à rua numa comemoração que aproxima o público dos cientistas. A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores (NEI) vai chegar a nove localidades de todo o país - Alcanena, Braga, Bragança, Estremoz, Lagos, Lisboa, Oeiras, Porto, Vila Nova de Foz Côa - com várias atividades experimentais e lúdicas para públicos de todas as idades, conversas com investigadores, desafios para o futuro, e histórias reais de quem conseguiu fintar a morte graças à ciência.

Já decorreram ao longo de agosto uma série de atividades de promoção, que se prolongaram durante todo o mês de setembro. O programa definitivo e todas as novidades serão divulgadas ao longo dos próximos dias no [website e redes sociais](#) da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://linktr.ee/noitedosinvestigadores>

Conheça aqui o programa com todas as atividades da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores:

Programa Alcanena: <https://alviela.cienciaviva.pt/14005/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2024>

Programa Braga: <https://www.casacienciabraga.org/nei2024>

Programa Bragança: <https://braganca.cienciaviva.pt/12334/nei-2024-2025>

Programa Estremoz: <https://www.ccvestremoz.com/nei-2024>

Programa Lagos: <https://lagos.cienciaviva.pt/13991/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2024>

Programa Lisboa: <https://www.pavconhecimento.pt/nei/2024>

Programa Oeiras: <https://www.itqb.unl.pt/events/european-researchers-night-2024/programa>

National press release (only in portuguese):

Nota de imprensa

Para divulgação imediata

Noite de festa da Ciência em todo o país

Admirar as estrelas, participar em escape rooms, identificar rochas, crustáceos, bivalves e corais, passear de barco, voar como uma águia, visitar o mundo das abelhas, experimentar simuladores de condução, degustar um menu com «pegada reduzida» e criar uma orquestra de sons são apenas algumas das atividades da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores. E isto é só uma amostra de uma vasta programação que promete surpreender e envolver o público em experiências imersivas de ciência e tecnologia. Está pronto para aceitar o desafio e entrar no fascinante mundo da investigação científica?

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Programa Estremoz: <https://www.ccvestremoz.com/nei-2024>

Programa Lagos: <https://lagos.cienciaviva.pt/13991/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2024>

Programa Lisboa: <https://www.pavconhecimento.pt/nei/2024>

Programa Oeiras: <https://www.itqb.unl.pt/events/european-researchers-night-2024/programa>

Programa Porto: [https://webstorage.cienciaviva.pt/public/pt.cienciaviva.io/](https://webstorage.cienciaviva.pt/public/pt.cienciaviva.io/wwwcentros/2730_2c283346017f80d736d16a99652c5efe.pdf)

[wwwcentros/2730_2c283346017f80d736d16a99652c5efe.pdf](https://webstorage.cienciaviva.pt/public/pt.cienciaviva.io/wwwcentros/2730_2c283346017f80d736d16a99652c5efe.pdf)
Programa Vila Nova de Foz Côa: <https://arte-coa.pt/ciencia-viva/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores/>

Sobre a Noite dos Investigadores:

A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores (NEI) é uma iniciativa promovida e financiada pela Comissão Europeia, no âmbito das Ações Marie Curie, que pretende aproximar cientistas e restante sociedade na última sexta-feira de setembro e assim partilhar um pouco o dia a dia de quem faz e produz conhecimento. Desde a sua génese, em 2005, que a NEI se tem estabelecido como um evento de referência, cativando a cada edição milhões de participantes em atividades que mobilizam milhares de investigadores entusiasmados por partilhar o seu conhecimento e os resultados da sua investigação.

A edição para o biénio 2024-2025 surge com o acrónimo **EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools)** – uma oportunidade para os participantes usufruírem de uma variedade de eventos cuja temática se centra nas missões da União Europeia: Adaptação às alterações climáticas; Prevenção e tratamento de cancro; Recuperação do oceano e das águas;

Cidades inteligentes e com impacto neutro no clima; Transição para solos saudáveis.

O consórcio EU-EMBRACES é coordenado pelo ITQB Nova – Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier e tem como parceiros o i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde e a Rede Ciência Viva – Agência Nacional para a Cultura Científica e Tecnológica.

Mais informações

<https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/>

Contactos

Coordenadora

Ana Sanchez | ITQB NOVA – Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier:
asanchez@itqb.unl.pt

Equipa de Comunicação

Rute Verdade | i3s – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde – rute.verdade@i3s.up.pt
Mariana Campos | i3s – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde – mariana.campos@i3s.up.pt

Regional press release (only in portuguese):

Nota de imprensa

Para divulgação imediata

Noite de festa da Ciência em todo o país

Admirar as estrelas,

A 27 de setembro, a Ciência volta a sair à rua numa comemoração que aproxima o público dos cientistas. A Noite Europeia dos Investigadores (NEI) chegará a 9 localidades, um pouco por todo o país, onde os curiosos terão à sua espera várias iniciativas para pôr a mão na massa, conversar com investigadores e descobrir os desafios que o futuro nos reserva.

Num evento que conta com a coordenação do ITQB NOVA, haverá temas para todos os gostos: desde áreas ligadas à saúde, como o cancro, até ao impacto da ação humana no planeta, tais como as alterações climáticas, a conservação dos solos e dos oceanos e a crescente vertente das cidades inteligentes, indo ao encontro das cinco missões definidas como prioritárias pela União Europeia. Em [inserir localidade] teremos também uma noite repleta de surpresas. [incluir temas em destaque e atividades associadas, bem como o público a que se destina]

Já decorreram ao longo de agosto uma série de atividades de promoção, que se prolongaram durante todo o mês de setembro [apenas se nesta localidade ocorreram atividades de pré-evento]. O programa definitivo e todas as novidades serão divulgadas ao longo deste mês no website e redes sociais da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://linktr.ee/noitedosinvestigadores>. A informação será também disponibilizada no site oficial do site [site do centro e respectivas redes sociais].

Mais informações

<https://nei.cienciaviva.pt/2024/>

Contactos

Coordenação: Ana Sanchez | ITQB NOVA - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica
António Xavier: asanchez@itqb.unl.pt

Equipa de Comunicação: Rute Verdade | i3s - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde - rute.verdade@i3s.up.pt / Mariana Campos | i3s - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde - mariana.campos@i3s.up.pt

[Preencher com o nome e contacto do responsável local]

Sobre o consórcio:

O consórcio EU-EMBRACES é coordenado pelo ITQB Nova - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier e tem como parceiros o i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde e a Rede Ciência Viva - Agência Nacional para a Cultura Científica e Tecnológica.

<p>Localidade e atividades associadas (aplicável a apoios regionais)</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 40px; margin-bottom: 10px;"></div> <p>Em nome do consórcio EU-EMBRACES</p> <p>gostaríamos de solicitar a vossa associação ao evento, fundamental para a sua concretização e sucesso. De seguida, indicaremos algumas modalidades de apoio, ainda que estejamos disponíveis para analisar e discutir outras modalidades que possam considerar pertinentes.</p>	<p>Modalidades</p> <p>Apoiantes <input type="checkbox"/> Profissional ou instituição que oferece uma ajuda estratégica à concretização do projeto, nomeadamente através da prestação de um serviço, empréstimo de equipamento ou a disponibilização de um espaço.</p> <p>Parceiros <input type="checkbox"/> Instituições que unem forças em prol de um objetivo em comum, existindo troca de contrapartidas entre as entidades envolvidas.</p> <p>Patrocinadores <input type="checkbox"/> Instituições que investem no projeto, nomeadamente, em moldes pecuniários.</p>	<p>Contrapartidas aplicáveis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Inclusão do logótipo da entidade associada na página do website da NEI referente à atividade/localidade que apoia; <input type="checkbox"/> Inclusão do logótipo da entidade associada nos materiais promocionais (incluindo o programa) referentes à atividade/localidade que apoia; <input type="checkbox"/> Destaque nos componentes de redes sociais da localidade e/ou da NEI antes, durante e após o evento; <input type="checkbox"/> Inclusão do logótipo da entidade associada nas principais páginas do evento (website e redes sociais); <input type="checkbox"/> Inclusão do logótipo da entidade associada em todos os materiais de promoção do evento (como um todo ou localmente, dependendo da natureza da associação); <input type="checkbox"/> Publicações em parceria com as redes sociais da NEI/localidade; <input type="checkbox"/> Stands de exposição onde a entidade em questão pode interagir diretamente com o público e apresentar os seus produtos/serviços; <input type="checkbox"/> Participação em atividades; <input type="checkbox"/> Acesso a uma galeria de fotos e vídeos do evento, destacando a presença e envolvimento da entidade associada; <input type="checkbox"/> Inclusão do logótipo nos materiais educativos e kits cuja produção esteja associada ao evento; <input type="checkbox"/> Destaque em comunicações oficiais (a nível nacional ou regional dependendo da natureza da associação);
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3. | Visual materials

All relevant materials such as the event's branding materials, logos, and banners were sent to associate partners, venues, media and others to ensure consistency in media coverage.

Logo and its manual

The manual consists of 12 pages detailing the visual identity for NEI 2024:

- Page 1:** Title page: 'MANUAL DE IDENTIDADE VISUAL NOITE EUROPEIA DOS INVESTIGADORES'. Includes a small logo and introductory text.
- Page 2:** 'Logomarca articulação vertical' showing three vertical logo variations.
- Page 3:** 'Logomarca articulação horizontal' showing three horizontal logo variations.
- Page 4:** 'Logomarca articulação horizontal' showing the logo with decorative elements like a moon and a plant.
- Page 5:** 'Logomarca margens de segurança' showing the logo with grid lines indicating safe zones.
- Page 6:** 'Logomarca margens de segurança' showing the logo with a dark background and safety margins.
- Page 7:** 'Codificação cromática' showing color swatches for primary colors (yellow, purple) and secondary colors (white, black) with their respective hex codes.
- Page 8:** 'Codificação tipográfica utilização impressa' showing font specifications and a 'DOWNLOAD DA FONTE AQUI' button.
- Page 9:** 'Logomarca uso incorreto' showing the logo with a red 'X' over it, indicating incorrect usage.
- Page 10:** 'Logomarca uso incorreto' showing the logo tilted or distorted, indicating incorrect usage.
- Page 11:** 'Logomarca comportamento sobre fundos de cor da marca' showing the logo placed on various colored backgrounds.
- Page 12:** 'Logomarca comportamento sobre fundos de cor' showing the logo placed on various colored backgrounds.

Banners

Youtube banner

X and Facebook banner

Social media templates

Pre-events and ERN templates

After pre-events watermark

Postcard

NOITE DOS INVESTIGADORES
27 set 2024

rrqb nova 3s Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde Universidade do Porto CIÊNCIA VIVA Agência Nacional para a Ciência e Tecnologia Funded by the European Union

Projeto financiado pela União Europeia. Os pontos de vista e opiniões expressos são da exclusiva responsabilidade do(s) autor(es) e não refletem necessariamente as do União Europeia ou da Agência de Inovação do Conselho Europeu de Investigação. Nem a União Europeia nem a autoridade que concede o financiamento podem ser responsabilizadas por eles.

Invitation

27 SET 2024
CIDADE
Local

>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Nunc et sapien ac diam aliquam suscipit in id lacus. Quisque malesuada finibus erat, non consequat eros finibus nec. Cras feugiat tellus nec ullamcorper rhoncus. Sed elementum ornare augue, gravida commodo tortor hendrerit mollis. Nulla vitae diam eget nunc efficitur facilisis. Mauris maximus consectetur sagittis. Praesent odio risus, finibus pretium fringilla a, aliquam sit amet justo.

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nei.cienciaviva.pt @neinvestigadores @noitedosinvestigadores @NEI_pt Noite dos Investigadores

ERN program – Instagram and Facebook

<p>PRO- GRA -MA 20 24</p>	<p>SEXTA Braga 27 Planetário - Casa da Ciência de Braga</p> <hr/> <p>15:00 OFICINA TEMÁTICA "A IMPORTÂNCIA DAS ZONAS HÚMIDAS"</p> <hr/> <p>17:00 BIOBLITZ NA CERCA DO MOSTEIRO DE TIBÃES</p> <hr/> <p>19:00 ACREDITAÇÃO DOS PARTICIPANTES, MONTAGEM DOS TELESCÓPIOS E PREPARAÇÃO DA OBSERVAÇÃO NOTURNA</p> <hr/> <p>21:00 JOSÉ AUGUSTO MATOS "UMA VIAGEM PELO UNIVERSO"</p> <hr/> <p>21:15 GRANDE ENCONTRO DE TELESCÓPIOS</p>	<p>SEXTA Oeiras 27 Marina de Oeiras</p> <hr/> <p>16:00 BANCAS DE CIÊNCIA 22:00</p> <hr/> <p>16:00 PROVA DE VINHO VILLA OEIRAS ESPAÇO OEIRAS VALLEY</p> <hr/> <p>17:30 DESAFIOS CIENTÍFICOS</p> <hr/> <p>16:00 OUTBREAK ROOM - EVAMOB'S 22:00</p> <hr/> <p>19:00 APRESENTAÇÃO MUSICAL DAS BATUCADEIRAS "VOZ DI CULTURA"</p>
<p>SEXTA Lisboa 27 Pavilhão do Conhecimento - Centro Ciência Viva</p> <hr/> <p>18:00 CAMINHO DA LUZ 23:30</p> <hr/> <p>18:00 EXPLORADORES DE SOMBRAS 00:15</p> <hr/> <p>18:00 COMIDA DE CONFORTO 00:15</p> <hr/> <p>18:00 FOTOGRAFIAS EUROPEIAS 23:00</p> <hr/> <p>23:45 A CIÊNCIA E A MÚSICA 00:15</p>	<p>SEXTA Lagos 27 Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos</p> <hr/> <p>18:00 ATIVIDADES DE SENSIBILIZAÇÃO PARA AS ADAPTAÇÕES ÀS ALTERAÇÕES CLIMÁTICAS</p> <hr/> <p>18:30 MOMENTO MUSICAL COM BLACKBIRD DUO</p> <hr/> <p>19:00 CONVERSAS COM INVESTIGADORES SOBRE AS ALTERAÇÕES CLIMÁTICAS</p> <hr/> <p>20:00 DEGUSTAÇÃO DE UM MENU COM "PEGADA REDUZIDA" COM PRODUTOS LOCAIS</p> <hr/> <p>20:30 MOMENTO MUSICAL COM BLACKBIRD DUO</p>	<p>SEXTA Porto 27 i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde</p> <hr/> <p>18:00 i3S DEMONSTRAÇÕES E ATIVIDADES EXPERIMENTAIS</p> <hr/> <p>18:45 AUDITÓRIO ALTERAÇÕES CLIMÁTICAS E DEMOGRÁFICAS</p> <hr/> <p>21:00 AUDITÓRIO CANCRO HEREDIÁRIO: NASCER COM A ESPADA SOBRE A CABEÇA</p> <hr/> <p>22:00 AUDITÓRIO O BARCO SALVA-VIDAS - DEBATE PELA SOBREVIVÊNCIA</p>
<p>SEXTA Estremoz 27 Centro Ciência Viva de Estremoz</p> <hr/> <p>EXPOSIÇÃO: HOMO UM FAZEDOR DE OBJETOS...</p> <hr/> <p>CONVERSAS SOBRE O ANTROPOCÊNICO!?... UMA GRANDE HISTÓRIA...</p>	<p>SEXTA Braga 27 Planetário Casa da Ciência de Braga</p> <hr/> <p>15:00 OFICINA TEMÁTICA "A IMPORTÂNCIA DAS ZONAS HÚMIDAS"</p> <hr/> <p>17:00 BIOBLITZ NA CERCA DO MOSTEIRO DE TIBÃES</p> <hr/> <p>19:00 ACREDITAÇÃO DOS PARTICIPANTES, MONTAGEM DOS TELESCÓPIOS E PREPARAÇÃO DA OBSERVAÇÃO NOTURNA</p> <hr/> <p>21:00 JOSÉ AUGUSTO MATOS "UMA VIAGEM PELO UNIVERSO"</p> <hr/> <p>21:15 GRANDE ENCONTRO DE TELESCÓPIOS</p>	

ERN program – X

Example of ERN album cover for Facebook

4. | Clipping list

National

- 15/09/2024 – Press Clipping – CM TV: Falar Global – ‘Festa da Ciência’: Noite europeia dos investigadores aproxima cientistas do público - https://www.cm-tv.pt/programas/informacao/falar-global/detalhe/festa-da-ciencia-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-aproxima-cientistas-do-publico?ref=Pesquisa_Destaques
- 20/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Notícias ao Minuto Online – Dezenas de atividades para aproximar público da ciência na próxima semana - <https://www.noticiasao minuto.com/pais/2635947/dezenas-de-atividades-para-aproximar-publico-da-ciencia-na-proxima-semana>
- 20/09/2024 – Press Clipping – The News Portugal – Dezenas de atividades para aproximar público da ciência na próxima semana - <https://thenews.co.pt/dezenas-de-atividades-para-aproximar-publico-da-ciencia-na-proxima-semana/>
- 23/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Comunidade Cultura e Arte – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores: a noite em que se celebra a ciência - https://comunidadeculturaearte.com/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-a-noite-em-que-se-celebra-a-ciencia/#google_vignette
- 25/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Redação diárioOnline Região Sul – Noite de festa da Ciência em todo o país incluindo em Lagos - <https://regiao-sul.pt/educacao-e-ciencia/noite-de-festa-da-ciencia-em-todo-o-pais-incluindo-em-lagos/684089>
- 25/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Mais Algarve - CCV de Lagos | Noite Europeia Dos Investigadores 2024? Noite de festa da ciência em todo o país - <https://maisalgarve.pt/2024/09/25/ccv-de-lagos-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2024-noite-de-festa-da-ciencia-em-todo-o-pais/>
- 27/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Público – É a Noite Europeia dos Investigadores. Há atividades gratuitas para todos os gostos - <https://www.publico.pt/2024/09/27/ciencia/noticia/noite-europeia-investigadores-ha-actividades-gratuitas-gostos-2105664>

Oeiras – ITQB NOVA

- 24/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Marinha.pt – Aquário Vasco da Gama na Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://www.marinha.pt/pt/media-center/Noticias/Paginas/Aquario-Vasco-da-Gama-na-Noite-Europeia-dos-Investigadores.aspx>
- 25/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Oeiras Digital – NEI Oeiras 24. Oeiras Marina será palco da Noite Europeia dos Investigadores - <https://oeirasdigital.pt/onei-oeiras-24-oeiras-marina-sera-palco-da-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores/>
- 26/09/2024 – Press Clipping – New in Oeiras (nit) – Marina de Oeiras recebe noite dedicada à ciência com jogos, escape room e stand up - <https://newinoeiras.nit.pt/na-cidade/marina-de-oeiras-recebe-noite-dedicada-a-ciencia-com-jogos-escape-room-e-stand-up/>
- 27/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Oeiras Valley | Município de Oeiras – Noite dos Investigadores – NEI Oeiras 24 - <https://www.oeiras.pt/-/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-setembro-2024>
- 30/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Oeiras Valley | Município de Oeiras – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores: Ciência e Inovação em Oeiras - <https://www.oeiras.pt/-/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores>

Parque das nações – Pavilhão do Conhecimento

20/09/2024 – Press Clipping – TV Europa – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores no Pavilhão do Conhecimento - <https://www.tveuropa.pt/noticias/noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-tem-encontro-marcado-no-pavilhao-do-conhecimento/>

20/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Pumpkin – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores no Pavilhão do Conhecimento! - <https://pumpkin.pt/eventos/nei-pavilhao-do-conhecimento/>

22/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Parque das Nações – Junta de Freguesia – Noite Europeia dos Investigadores no Ciência Viva - <https://www.jf-parquedasnacoes.pt/autarquia/noticias/1182-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-no-ciencia-viva>

Porto – i3S

20/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Notícias Universidade do Porto – Noite dos Investigadores 2024 junta instituições da U.Porto no i3S - <https://noticias.up.pt/2024/09/20/noite-dos-investigadores-2024-junta-instituicoes-da-u-porto-no-i3s/>

23/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Viva! O Grande Porto Online – Porto lança um convite irresistível: uma noite mágica de ciência e aventuras! - https://viva-porto.pt/porto-lanca-um-convite-irresistivel-uma-noite-magica-de-ciencia-e-aventuras/#google_vignette

30/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Notícias Universidade do Porto – Á Noite, no laboratório ... - <https://noticias.up.pt/foto-da-semana/a-noite-no-laboratorio/>

Braga

19/09/2024 – Press Clipping – O Minho – Braga recebe grande encontro de telescópios para “espreitar o universo” - <https://maisalgarve.pt/2024/09/06/ccv-lagos-noite-europeia-dos-investigadores-2024/>

28/09/2024 – Press Clipping – Correio do Minho – Centro de Ciência Viva de Braga celebrou a NEI 2024 a olhar para o Universo - https://correiodominho.pt/noticias/centro-ciencia-viva-de-braga-celebrou-a-nei-2024-a-olhar-para-o-universo/155754?fbclid=IwY2xjawFID9JleHRuA2FlbQIxMQABHe3mPrLzHzNIMdgd4_cDVVWVl-buKZQJ_s0l3E0yxqbVRxKHHmNg4L9fvA_aem_BIGiqA64GtvC_HMTt0llbQ&sfnsn=mo

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Bragança

N/a

Museu do Côa

N/a

Lagos

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Estremoz

N/a

Alcanena

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